

T2K²: a System for Automatically Extracting and Organizing Knowledge from Texts

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Abstract

In this paper, we present T2K², a suite of tools for automatically extracting domain-specific knowledge from collections of Italian and English texts. T2K² (Text–To–Knowledge v2) relies on a battery of tools for Natural Language Processing (NLP), statistical text analysis and machine learning which are dynamically integrated to provide an accurate and incremental representation of the content of vast repositories of unstructured documents. Extracted knowledge ranges from domain-specific entities and named entities to the relations connecting them and can be used for indexing document collections with respect to different information types. T2K² also includes “linguistic profiling” functionalities aimed at supporting the user in constructing the acquisition corpus, e.g. in selecting texts belonging to the same genre or characterized by the same degree of specialization or in monitoring the “added value” of newly inserted documents. T2K² is a web application which can be accessed from any browser through a personal account which has been tested in a wide range of domains.

Keywords: Natural Language Processing, Information Extraction, Knowledge Management

1. Introduction

T2K² (Text–To–Knowledge v2) extracts domain-specific information from texts, provides a structured organisation of extracted knowledge and indexes document collections with respect to the automatically acquired information. It relies on a battery of tools for Natural Language Processing (NLP), statistical text analysis and machine learning which are dynamically integrated to provide an accurate representation of the domain-specific content of text corpora in different domains.

T2K² originates from the the ontology learning system named T2K (Text–to–Knowledge, Dell’Orletta et al. (2008), Lenci et al. (2009)) with a number of main novelties: i) it can be used to extract information from both Italian and English texts; ii) the linguistic pre-processing of texts is carried out by state-of-the-art NLP tools; iii) the range of performed knowledge extraction and organization tasks is wider; iv) it permits manual revision of results before more complex tasks are carried out.

T2K² can be accessed from any web browser through a personal account: it allows storing and managing uploaded corpora in a personal repository. By relying on a battery of linguistic pre-processing tools in charge of linguistically annotating uploaded corpora, T2K² performs three main knowledge extraction steps focusing on the extraction of domain-specific entities and of Named Entities as well as on the construction of a relation graph connecting them.

The main features of T2K² can be summarised as follows. First, it presents itself as a *self-service* system for information extraction which is configurable by following a simple and user-friendly configuration procedure where end-users can choose the domain-specific information to be extracted matching his/her own information needs. Secondly, it supports the user in the construction of corpora which are rep-

resentative of a given domain and/or are characterized by a homogeneous distribution of features representative of a specific textual genre or readability level. Thirdly, in T2K² the different levels of extracted information interact resulting in a *multi-dimensional* knowledge representation graph creating the prerequisites for sophisticated text mining processes that would be difficult to carry out if the levels of information were dealt with separately. To this end, T2K² uses a battery of tools and algorithms meant to visualizing, surfing and managing the knowledge graph. Last but not least, acquired knowledge can also be used for indexing document collections on the basis of extracted domain-specific entities, Named Entities and the relations connecting them. The index can be either used by T2K² to retrieve and visualize the text spans containing the information searched for by the user or downloaded and used as an input for external tools.

The paper focuses on the linguistic pre-processing and information extraction steps and on the automatic construction of the knowledge graph.

2. T2K²

Figure 1 provides an overall picture of the T2K² workflow. As it can be seen, T2K² encompasses two main sets of modules, respectively devoted to carry out the linguistic pre-processing of the acquisition corpus and to extract domain knowledge from the linguistically annotated texts. Once the user has uploaded a collection of documents, multi-level linguistic pre-processing is carried out. The linguistically analyzed corpus is used by the linguistic profiling module to support the user in evaluating its homogeneity and representativeness: at this level of analysis, the user can exploit the linguistic profiling results to validate the internal composition of the corpus while extending it with new texts. Once the acquisition corpus has been defined, knowledge

extraction is performed in three different steps, aimed at acquiring domain-specific entities, Named Entities and the relations linking them. T2K² exploits acquired information to create a structured representation of the input text and to index it with respect to the extracted information: the different information types extracted from the text are organized in a knowledge graph that can be visualized and surfed. The results of the linguistic pre-processing and knowledge extraction steps can be downloaded for inspection by the user who can correct and upload them back into the system in order to proceed in the workflow on the basis of the manually checked results.

2.1. Linguistic Pre-processing of Corpora

2.1.1. Linguistic Analysis

In T2K² linguistic pre-processing of texts is performed by a battery of annotation tools developed by the ItaliaNLP Lab and the Department of Computer Science of the University of Pisa. Each uploaded text is linguistically annotated at increasingly complex levels of analysis, represented by sentence splitting, tokenization, Part-Of-Speech tagging and dependency parsing. In particular, morpho-syntactic tagging is carried out by the POS tagger described in Dell'Orletta (2009) and dependency parsing by the DeSR parser (Attardi, 2006) using Support Vector Machine and Multilayer Perceptron as learning algorithms: as reported in Dell'Orletta (2009) and Attardi and Dell'Orletta (2009), both of them represent state-of-the-art tools for Italian and English. The results of the part-of-speech tagging and of the dependency parsing steps can be downloaded by the user in CoNLL format (Nivre et al., 2007), where *a*) sentences are separated by a blank line and *b*) each token starts on a new line and it is annotated with the following information types: lemma, coarse and fine grained parts of speech, morphological features and syntactic dependency information.

2.1.2. Linguistic Profiling

T2K² carries out the “linguistic profiling” (van Halteren, 2004) of the collection of texts to be used as acquisition corpus. Linguistic profiling consists in gathering statistics for a wide range of features spanning across different levels of linguistic description (i.e. lexical, morpho-syntactic and syntactic) which can be reliably extracted from automatically analyzed texts with the final aim of reconstructing the text profile. In particular, this pre-processing step is based on the “linguistic profiling” methodology described in Dell'Orletta et al. (2013) and within T2K² it is meant to support the user in the construction of his/her domain-specific corpus by investigating its underlying linguistic features. It can be usefully exploited, for example, to build corpora containing a homogeneous distribution of linguistic characteristics typically associated with a specific textual genre, since it is a widely acknowledged fact that the extraction of domain entities is affected by the degree of specialization of domain corpora (see, among others, Cabrè (1999)). Linguistic profiling results can also be exploited to monitor the “added value” of newly inserted documents: for this purpose, measures of vocabulary variation such as e.g. the type/token ratio (TTR) can be exploited, as demon-

strated by Caruso et al. (2014).

2.2. Extraction of Domain-Specific Knowledge

The first two steps of the Knowledge Extraction module are devoted to extract domain-specific entities denoting domain-specific concepts (see Section 2.2.1.) as well as Named Entities specific to the domain under analysis (see Section 2.2.2.). The input corpora are annotated and indexed with respect to the extracted information.

2.2.1. Domain-Specific Entities

The extraction of domain-specific terms denoting domain entities follows the methodology described in Bonin et al. (2010). By default, the automatically POS-tagged and lemmatized text is searched for candidate domain-specific terms, expressed by either single nominal terms or complex nominal structures with modifiers (typically, adjectival and prepositional modifiers), where the latter are retrieved on the basis of a set of POS patterns encoding morpho-syntactic templates for multi-word terms. According to the default configuration, T2K² extracts domain-specific entities typically expressed through nominal (either single or complex) terms. The domain relevance of multi-word terms is weighted on the basis of the C-NC value (Frantzi and Ananiadou, 1999) score, currently considered as a state-of-the-art method for terminology extraction.

Once a shortlist of well-formed and relevant candidate terms denoting domain entities is extracted from a given target corpus, the user can decide whether to apply the term extraction contrastive method, introduced in Bonin et al. (2010): candidate terms are first searched for in an automatically POS-tagged and lemmatized corpus representative of a different domain and are then weighted on the basis of the C-NC Value; the list of extracted terms is revised afterwards and re-ranked with respect to the associated contrastive score, reflecting their domain relevance which was computed on the basis of the inter-domain distribution of terms. The corpora to be used for the contrastive analysis step are selected among those previously uploaded by the user.

Besides nominal terms, T2K² also allows the identification of domain-specific properties and events which are expressed in the text through different sequences of POS patterns, headed e.g. by adjectives or verbs: the user can enforce POS-restrictions concerning the start-, internal- and final-token of the POSs sequences to be used for identifying candidate terms, and can also define thresholds for what concerns the length of multi-word terms as well as the amount of single and multi-word terms to be extracted. At the end of this extraction step, the user can download the list of extracted terms denoting domain-specific entities with an associated domain-relevance score calculated with respect to the whole acquisition corpus. The user can correct the list by pruning the erroneous or simply not relevant terms and re-upload the revised list into the system to proceed with the following analysis steps which will be carried out on the basis of the manually revised data.

The (possibly revised) list of extracted terms denoting domain-specific entities is then used to perform *entity indexing*: the results of this step are represented by a glossary

Figure 1: T2K² workflow.

of the acquired domain-specific terms and an index of the input documents with respect to the extracted terminology. For each term in the glossary, the following information types are provided: the prototypical form, corresponding to the term form most frequently attested in the acquisition corpus, the lemmatized form and the frequency of occurrence of the term (in all attested forms) within the whole document collection. As pointed out in Lenci et al. (2009), the choice of representing a domain term through its prototypical form rather than the lemma (as typically done in ordinary dictionaries) follows from the assumption that a bootstrapped glossary should reflect the actual usage of terms in texts: in fact, domain-specific meanings are often associated with a particular morphological form of a given term (e.g. plural). The index is in tabular format where each column contains the following information types:

- the prototypical form of the indexed entity;
- the identifiers of the document and of the sentence containing the entity mention as well as of the start-token;
- the length of the term denoting the entity (calculated in terms of tokens);
- the variants of the indexed entity attested within the input corpus. Following Nenadic et al. (2004) and Lenci et al. (2009), different types of term variation are considered, i.e. orthographic, morphological as well as structural.
- the TF/IDF score (Salton and Buckley, 1988) measuring the relevance of the indexed entity with respect to the specific document.

Both the glossary and the index can be downloaded by the user for them to be used as input for external tools. In addition, T2K² allows downloading the input corpora in

CoNLL format where the start-, internal- and final-token of the POSs sequences representing each domain term are annotated using the IOB labeling format (Ramshaw and Marcus, 1995), where the start-token is annotated with “B” (marking the begin of the entity mention), the internal- and final-tokens with “I” (marking the internal tokens) and all other tokens with “O”.

2.2.2. Named Entities

T2K² includes a multi-lingual module to extract Named Entities called ItaliaNLP NER. This module is a classifier based on Support Vector Machines using LIBSVM (Chang and Lin, 2001) that assigns a named entity tag to a token or a sequence of tokens. ItaliaNLP NER uses 5 kinds of features:

- orthographic features, i.e. the orthographic characteristics of the analyzed token, e.g. capitalized letters, presence of non-alphabetical characters, etc.;
- linguistic features, i.e. lemma, Part-Of-Speech, prefix and suffix of the analyzed token;
- dictionary look-up features, marking whether the analyzed token is part of an entity name occurring in one of the “People”, “Organization” and “Geo-political” gazetteers. The “Organizations” and “People” gazetteers were automatically generated from Wikipedia¹, while the “Geo-political” gazetteer was downloaded from the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe web site².
- contextual features, referring to orthographic, linguistic and dictionary look-up features of the context words of the analyzed token(s);

¹http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Lists_of_organizations and http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lists_of_people

²<http://www.unece.org/cefact/locode/welcome.html>

- non-local features: starting from the assumption that identical tokens in the same document very likely refer to the same entity, we used this feature type to exploit previous label assignments to predict the label for the token being analysed. The effectiveness of these *history* features is corroborated by what observed in Ratinov and Roth (2009), where the authors affirm that the named entities in the beginning of the documents tend to be more easily identifiable.

For Italian, ItaliaNLP NER is trained on I-CAB (Italian Content Annotation Treebank) (Magnini et al., 2006), the dataset used in the NER Task at EVALITA 2009 (Speranza, 2009) including four standard named entity tags, i.e. Person, Organization, Location and Geo-political entity. For English, the system is trained on the REUTERS corpus (Lewis et al., 2004), the dataset used in the CoNLL-2003 shared task focusing on language-independent named entity recognition (Sang and Meulder, 2003) and including four types of named entities: Persons, Locations, Organizations and Miscellaneous entities, i.e. that do not belong to the previous three groups. The results obtained for the two languages are in line with the state of the art when compared with the systems that participated to the EVALITA and CoNLL-2003 shared tasks.

At the end of this extraction step, the user can download the list of extracted named entities with associated classification, absolute and relative frequency; relative frequency information is reported with respect to both all classes and the assigned class. As in the case of domain-entities, T2K² allows downloading the input corpora in CoNLL format where the start-, internal- and final-tokens of the sequences representing each named entity are annotated using the IOB labeling format.

The list of extracted named entities is used to carry out *Named Entity indexing*, which results in an index in tabular format where each column contains the following information types:

- the indexed named entity;
- the identifiers of the document and of the sentence in which the named entity is mentioned as well as of the start-token;
- the length of the named entity calculated in terms of tokens;
- the semantic class of the named entity;
- the TF/IDF score (Salton and Buckley, 1988) measuring the relevance of the indexed named entity with respect to the specific document.

The user can download the index and use it as input for external tools.

2.3. Knowledge Organization and Knowledge Graph Construction

In T2K² extracted knowledge is organized at different levels. As in the previous T2K version, the extracted domain-specific terms are organized into fragments of taxonomical chains, grouping terms which share the semantic head

(e.g. *health research, international research, cancer research* are classified as hyponyms of the more general term *research*). Other types of organization are currently being investigated: for instance, terms are grouped on the basis of shared modifiers defining their scope (e.g. *research projects, research excellence, research infrastructure, research results* where *research* is the shared modifier).

The extracted domain-specific entities and named entities are also organized in a knowledge graph where the arcs linking the entities correspond to relations extracted from the analyzed corpus. Currently, in T2K² two different types of relations can be extracted: co-occurrence and similarity relations. The former is the case of relations holding between entity mentions co-occurring within the same context. To this end, different types of contexts can be selected, ranging from the whole document to the sentence or a span defined on the basis of a given number of tokens: in the future, a more linguistically oriented notion of context will also be used. The resulting knowledge graph is weighted with respect to the frequency of occurrence or using the log-likelihood metric for binomial distributions as defined in (Dunning, 1993). This notion of *context* makes T2K² robust with respect to non-canonical input, such as e.g. the language of social media, microblogs, etc., and enables the system to capture both inter- and intra-sentence relations. The risk that the system may also capture not relevant relations holding between entities casually co-occurring within the same context is limited by the fact that T2K² is meant to be used on big corpora where the statistics is supposed to highly reduce the impact of these events.

On the other hand, similarity relations are computed on the basis of the amount of contexts shared by the same entity mentions. This kind of relations is weighted on the basis of the cosine similarity between the entity context vectors. The components of each vector contain the association strength (computed in terms of log-likelihood) between the considered entity and its context entities.

T2K² allows visualizing the whole knowledge graph or sub-graphs created by selecting a sub-set of entities. The knowledge graph can also be filtered on the basis of relations' weight, where the relations are weighted according to their frequency, log-likelihood or cosine similarity, and on the basis of the entities' frequency. The resulting graph can be used in a number of different graph mining analysis, such as e.g. extraction of all relations involving a given entity, or extraction of sub-graphs containing a given entity, or extraction of relations shared by two or more entities, or extraction of entities which share the same relations. The input corpus is indexed afterwards on the basis of extracted relations and entities. Accordingly, T2K² allows visualizing the text spans of the input corpus mentioning the extracted entity and/or relation.

2.4. Output Examples

In this section, we exemplify the output of the different information extraction steps described in Sections 2.2. and 2.3., using as acquisition corpus a collection of educational textbooks for high school on Italian art history.³

³The corpus was built in the framework of the *iSLe - intelligent Semantic Liquid eBook*, <http://www.progettoisle.it/il->

Figure 2 exemplifies the output of the term extraction step, where terms are ordered on the basis of their domain relevance within the input corpus: for each term the absolute frequency is also reported. Figure 3 shows a fragment of the index. The terms are alphabetically ordered: each line refers to a single occurrence of a given term within a document. For example, the multi-word term *architettura greca* ‘Greek architecture’ occurs in five lines, four times in the *Storia dell’Arte 4* volume and one time in the *Storia dell’Arte 5* volume. The column reporting the *TF/IDF* score shows that this entity is more relevant in the *Storia dell’Arte 4* volume, with a score of 0.00704 (against 0.0046 for the other volume).

In Figure 4 the domain-specific terms are organized into fragments of taxonomical chains, for example *architettura greca* ‘Greek architecture’, *architettura longobarda* ‘Longobard architecture’, *architettura romana* ‘Roman architecture’, *architettura romanica* ‘Romanesque architecture’ share the same semantic head *architettura* ‘architecture’. A short list of extracted named entities (ordered by decreasing frequency) is reported in Figure 5, with each line containing a single entity mention.

Figure 6 shows the visualization of the Knowledge graph, where domain-specific terms and named entities are represented by nodes, and the relations linking them by arcs. The different entity types are marked by different colors, whereas the size of nodes is proportional to the frequency of the corresponding entity. T2K² allows the user to create graph views focusing on specific relation types (i.e. co-occurrence or similarity) and using different weight measures (i.e. frequency or log-likelihood). As described in Section 2.3., T2K² permits the visualization of sub-graphs of selected entities and/or relations: this is exemplified in Figure 7 showing the sub-graph of the *Person (PER) Giotto*, while Figure 8 reports the relations shared by two named entities, i.e. *Giotto* and *Cimabue*. Figure 9 reports a T2K² screenshot with a ternary relation linking *Giotto* and *Cimabue* with the domain specific entity *basilica superiore* ‘superior basilica’. The textual box reports the text span mentioning the extracted relation: it is said that *Giotto* and *Cimabue* decorated the superior basilica of St. Francesco in Assisi in different periods.

3. Ongoing Applications

T2K² is currently being tested and specialized in the framework of different ongoing projects aimed at extracting and organizing knowledge from different Italian domain-specific corpora:

- *Legal Text Mining: building semantic networks to support advanced queries in legal textual corpora (JURNET)*, a project funded by the Tuscany Region and aimed at accessing the knowledge contained in case law corpora;
- *iSLe – intelligent Semantic Liquid eBook*, a project funded by the Tuscany Region and aimed at i) developing an innovative software platform for digital educational publishing augmented with NLP-based

Prototypical Form	Lemma of Term	Frequency
opera	opera	167
tempio	tempio	135
edifici	edificio	128
mondo greco	mondo greco	31
arte greca	arte greco	21
figura umana	figura umano	21
produzione artistica	produzione artistico	16
apparato scultoreo	apparato scultoreo	16
struttura architettonica	struttura architettonico	16
arte romana	arte romano	15
architettura greca	architettura greco	15
architettura romanica	architettura romanico	15

Figure 2: An excerpt of the glossary with extracted domain-specific terms.

Prototypical form	Document ID	Sentence ID	Start Token ID	Length	Variant	TF*IDF
apparato scultoreo	Storia dell'arte 4	539	21	2	apparato scultoreo	0.0105718393966
apparato scultoreo	Storia dell'arte 4	537	29	2	apparato scultoreo	0.0105718393966
apparato scultoreo	Storia dell'arte 4	638	2	2	apparato scultoreo	0.0105718393966
apparato scultoreo	Storia dell'arte 6	990	2	2	apparato scultoreo	0.0105495828926
apparato scultoreo	Storia dell'arte 6	990	11	2	apparato scultoreo	0.0105495828926
architettura greca	Storia dell'arte 4	242	2	2	architettura greca	0.00704789293106
architettura greca	Storia dell'arte 4	267	7	2	architettura greca	0.00704789293106
architettura greca	Storia dell'arte 4	655	39	2	architettura greca	0.00704789293106
architettura greca	Storia dell'arte 4	699	23	2	architettura greca	0.00704789293106
architettura greca	Storia dell'arte 5	286	12	2	architettura greca	0.0046057462077

Figure 3: An excerpt of the term index.

functionalities for knowledge management and at ii) supporting authors during the creation of educational textbooks using the knowledge graph extracted from domain-specific corpora;

- *INMOTO: Information and MObility for Tourism*, a national Italian project where T2K² is used to create an ontology of tourism supporting the writing of travel guides on the basis of the knowledge extracted from web touristic sites.

Figure 6: A screenshot of the extracted knowledge graph.

T2K² is also being tested on English texts in studies focused on the analysis of technical documents such as patents and system requirements with the final aim of helping engineers to discover relevant concepts and relations:

- The contrastive analysis performed by T2K² was used by Ferrari et al. (2013) to extract domain-specific entities from brochures. Identifying and comparing the features provided by the other vendors might greatly help during the market analysis. However, mining common and variant features of from the publicly available documents of the competitors is a time consuming and error-prone task. In this scenario, they used the domain specific entities extracted by T2K² to perform commonality and variability mining. A case study was carried out to qualitatively evaluate the approach in the metro systems domain: the proposed approach demonstrated its expected time-effectiveness.
- T2K² was used to detect and extract information about the functions, the physical behaviour and the states of the system directly from patents (Fantoni et al. (2013)). In the field of automatic patent analysis a number of domain specific ontologies have been successfully proposed in a variety of research projects, mostly focusing on upper level concepts hand-crafted by domain experts. However, realistically large knowledge-based applications need com-

prehensive ontologies that should be continuously updated. To overcome this problem, they used the terminology extraction approach developed by T2K² on automatically crawling patents belonging to specified patent classes and subclasses for automatically acquiring a collection of entities characterizing the analyzed domain. Acquired entities were used to create a knowledge base representing a key ingredient in the proposed approach to disambiguate, gather, select and organize information from technical documents.

- Ferrari et al. (2014) applied T2K² on system requirements specifications. They proposed two metrics that take into account the relevant terms of the input documents, and the relevant relationships among terms to measure and improve the completeness of the requirements with respect to the input documents of the requirements definition phase, such as preliminary specifications, transcripts of meetings with the customers, etc. They use T2K² within their system named Completeness Assistant for Requirements (CAR) to extract relevant concepts and relations mentioned in the input documents.

4. Further Directions of Research

Current lines of research and development cover different areas. First, we are working towards the definition of innovative methods to extract and classify domain-specific

Brother-Narrower Terms	
Head Based	
architettura	architettura greca architettura longobarda architettura romana architettura romanica
arte	arte bizantina arte carolingia arte classica arte egizia arte ellenistica arte etrusca arte greca arte medio-italica arte ottoniana arte paleocristiana arte parietale arte preistorica arte romana arti figurative
città	città dell' Impero città di Roma città di Troia città greche città romana
colonne	colonna corinza colonna dorica colonne corinze colonne ioniche
edifici	edifici di culto edifici pubblici edifici religiosi edifici romanici edifici sacri

Figure 4: An excerpt of extracted taxonomical chains.

named entities; we are currently developing methods for clustering and labeling domain specific entities and for indexing the input document collection on the basis of them. For what concerns relation extraction, we are implementing linguistically driven methods relying on the syntactic structure of the text: T2K² will exploit linguistic information both to automatically extract domain-specific relations and to allow the user to define syntactic patterns conveying them. Last but not least, we are also devising methods for graph mining: in particular, we are integrating in T2K² algorithms for frequent subgraph mining, graph clustering and community discovery to detect graph areas that are thematically homogeneous as well as algorithms for detecting hub nodes in order to identify relevant topics of the input corpus.

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Name Entity Extraction				
Show	50	entries	Search:	
Entity	Class	Frequency	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Giotto	Person	66.0	7.61	15.64
Cimabue	Person	26.0	3.00	6.16
Roma	GeoPolitical Entity	21.0	2.42	7.02
Duccio	Person	21.0	2.42	4.98
Arnolfo	Person	18.0	2.08	4.27
Italia	GeoPolitical Entity	18.0	2.08	6.02
Assisi	GeoPolitical Entity	17.0	1.96	5.69
Francesco	Person	15.0	1.73	3.55
Siena	GeoPolitical Entity	15.0	1.73	5.02
Firenze	GeoPolitical Entity	14.0	1.61	4.68
Nicola	Person	12.0	1.38	2.84
Giovanni	Person	12.0	1.38	2.84
Giovanni Pisano	Person	10.0	1.15	2.37
Parigi	GeoPolitical Entity	10.0	1.15	3.34
Francia	GeoPolitical Entity	9.0	1.04	3.01
Simone Martini	Person	9.0	1.04	2.13

Figure 5: An excerpt of extracted Named Entities.

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Figure 7: The sub-graph of *Person* (PER) **Giotto**.

Figure 8: The relations involving the two named entities **Giotto** and **Cimabue**.

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Figure 9: The ternary relation linking *Giotto* and *Cimabue* with *basilica superiore* ‘superior basilica’.

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